

RESEARCH SOFTWARE ENGINEERING 2023

ANNUAL REPORT

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Welcome to the 2023 annual report for the Newcastle University Research Software Engineering Team.

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QUARTER ONE
JAN - MAR

OVERVIEW

The start of the year was all about growth into new areas and getting ourselves out there. We invested a lot of time speaking to different groups around the University and getting involved in different initiatives.

01

AHPC STEERING GROUP

The AHPC project started, and Mark is involved in the steering group. The project is tasked with creating a business case and specification for a new HPC machine to replace the current offering. Whilst HPC is not something we have traditionally done, RSE services were seen as core to the support offering around the new machine due to come online late 2024.

02

SPEAKING TOUR

The team started an outreach activity to reach more researchers. We took slots of different seminar series to speak directly to people about the RSE service.

03

LEADERSHIP PLAN

The leadership team submitted a paper to the faculty outlining some of the challenges being faced. Ultimately the faculty started a review of the team.

QUARTER TWO
APR - JUN

OVERVIEW

Spring was a period of firsts in different ways, trying out different ways of diversifying our services, growing our networks, and disseminating our work. We took on our first research software consultancy project, which we will seek to do more of in 2024.

01

CLIMATE CHAMP

Work starts on our first contract research software project for Viktoria Spaiser in Leeds. The project went on to create a mobile app that allowed users to track their carbon footprint throughout their day for an 8-week trial period, while receiving prompts to make small behavioural changes. This project was our first foray into research software consultancy.

02

KIM MARTIN VISIT

Kim Martin from Stellenbosch University in South Africa visited the UK to meet different RSE groups, spending a week in Newcastle.

03

NATURE MEDICINE COMMENT

Dave Horsfall was lead author on a comment article for Nature Medicine titled "*Research software engineering accelerates the translation of biomedical research for health*"

QUARTER THREE
JUL - SEP

OVERVIEW

Summer was a period of welcome validation from the wider community but also an immensely difficult period with a chronic lack of staff to deliver time-sensitive projects. The constraint of not being granted permission to recruit would not see relief until the last quarter of the year.

01

RSECON23

The team descended on Swansea for RSECon23. Several team members had spent many months contributing to the organising committee in different ways. For others, this was their first opportunity to meet and engage with the wider community and movement. Jannetta Steyn and Robin Nandi won awards for their community work in the last year. Mike Simpson was elected as Trustee of the RSE Society.

02

ROLLING RECRUITMENT

To deliver existing projects and meet demand for new work we were granted permission to pursue a rolling-recruitment strategy.

03

STAFF ATTRITION

Several staff members moved on to new roles outside the organisation, leading to an acute squeeze on staff availability to fulfil projects.

QUARTER FOUR
OCT - DEC

OVERVIEW

The end of the year was filled with activities that are the basis for big things in 2024. New staff to deliver more projects than ever, a new HPC machine arriving in late 2024 and RSECon returning to Newcastle in September next year.

01

RECRUITMENT

The final new starters arrived from the four month long recruitment campaign. Hundreds of applications were received, and all eight positions were filled across twelve interview rounds. On-boarding that many new staff in a short space of time presented challenges but also gave the team a new energy.

02

SUPERCOMPUTING

As part of research for the new HPC machine, Mark attended Super Computing 23 in Denver, Colorado.

03

RSECON24

Dave Horsfall was officially announced as the programme co-chair, along with Katie Finch of Exeter, for RSECon24 in Newcastle.

THE

**THE
FINANCES**

FINANCES

FINANCE
THE YEAR IN NUMBERS

The biggest improvement this year is in our long-term funding. We've been involved in more than 40 grants at the application stage and there is currently £2.3m worth of RSE time awaiting funding outcomes. To put that in context, the total income from every project we've completed since starting in 2019 is £2.1m

**FACILITY
INCOME**

£650K

Costs recovered using the facility day rate. This figure does not include staff directly charged to projects.

**GRANT
APPLICATIONS**

£2.3M

RSE facility time included on grants submitted this year and waiting outcomes.

SAGE

Supporting research worth

£18.8m

in the Science, Agriculture & Engineering Faculty

HASS

Supporting research worth

£561k

in the Humanities & Social Sciences Faculty

FMS

Supporting research worth

£10.1m

in the Medical Sciences Faculty

FINANCE

UTILISATION RATE

94.7% AVERAGE

High utilisation shows healthy demand and ability to hit income targets. However, it is far too high and is not sustainable in the long term. Our target is 80% and should never exceed 100%.

INCOME **COST RECOVERY**

The share of our income coming from facility charge out rates has broken 50% for the first time, rising to 63%. It is up from 45% in 2022 and 11% in 2021, continuing a strong upward trend. The ambition is to get that figure as high as possible while accepting it will never be 100% due to internal or post-award funding.

INCOME **AWARD STAGE**

Surprisingly, the share of post-award work we have taken on this year is up from 39% to 49%. Last year we suggested that it was high due to COVID and researchers looking for ways to spend existing grant money, so we expected it to go down this year. The rise is potentially to do with the speaking tour we embarked on, alerting more teams to our existence mid-grant.

INCOME **FACULTY**

In comparison, funding breakdown by faculty has remained fairly constant, with only a few percentage changes between each one. SAgE disciplines tend to be more computationally intensive, however we see Medical Sciences as a huge potential growth area that remains untapped.

THE

TEAM

Research Software
Engineer

DANIELA BASURTO LOZADA

Haniffa Lab

SKILLS

Python, JavaScript, C#, R, Pytorch, Shell, Matlab,
Git, GitHub Workflows

INTERESTS

Software Development, Web Development

Daniela joined the team in February 2022. She works on developing the cell atlas web application as well as other software tools to process and visualize the Haniffa lab's research data.

Daniela received her bachelor's degree in Computer Systems Engineering from Instituto Tecnológico de Querétaro, and a master's degree in Image Analysis from Mexico's Instituto Politécnico Nacional where she worked with machine learning and deep learning techniques. She also has experience in computer vision in the industry.

Research Software
Engineer

CARMELO CALAFIORE

Middleware & Data
Science Team

SKILLS

Python, Bash, MATLAB, JavaScript, HTML/CSS, C++, PyCharm, IntelliJ IDEA, Git/GitHub, Unix Shell, Blender, Inkscape

INTERESTS

Computer Vision, Cognitive Robotics, Computational Neuroscience, Modelling, Machine Learning, Deep Learning, Reinforcement Learning, Psychology and Cognitive Neuroscience, Statistics

Carmelo has a PhD from the University of Essex in the UK with a wide technical background that includes computer vision, machine learning, statistics, psychology, computational neuroscience, and cognitive robotics. His PhD was in vision, where he investigated and compared the active action recognition of robots and humans. The robots were recurrent convolutional neural networks optimised with supervisory learning to recognise the actions in dynamic videos and reinforcement learning to select the next-optimal viewpoints for action recognition.

Since joining the team in 2023, he has supported academic research with his expertise in machine learning, statistics, and data analysis.

Research Software
Engineer

FATIH CIGIRCI

Web & Mobile
Team

SKILLS

C#, JavaScript, TypeScript, HTML/CSS, Java, React, Node.js, Express, MongoDB, Visual Studio, MSSQL, Azure, Azure Functions, .NET (dotnet), ASP

INTERESTS

Solution Architect, DevOps, Web Development, UX Design

Fatih joined the Research Software Engineering team in March 2023.

He's an enthusiastic developer with over 5 years of professional experience across multiple industries. Someone who's always eager to: explore, experiment and learn new technologies.

He has previously worked within the .NET ecosystem working mostly on custom API's, Azure Functions, performant optimized code as a Solution Developer/DevOps.

A portrait of a woman with dark hair, smiling slightly, wearing a blue patterned top. The background is a light, neutral color.

Senior Research
Software Engineer

KATE COURT

Head of Middleware
& Data Science Team

SKILLS

JavaScript, TypeScript, HTML/CSS, Java, XML, XSLT, Angular, Node.js, eXist-db, Docker, MongoDB, Azure Functions, Terraform, GitHub Workflows

INTERESTS

Web Development

Kate is a full stack web developer who originally trained in the Arts before completing an MSc in Computer Science at Newcastle University in 2018. She joined the RSE team in 2019 and manages the Middleware and Data Science team.

Previously Kate led the project management of the Creative Fuse project at Northumbria University. She is technical lead on the NHS project Organ Quality Assessment (OrQA). During her time in the RSE team she has trained as a Software Carpentries instructor and supervised Masters level dissertation students. She has also designed and delivered an entry level digital skills course for local women.

Research Software
Engineer

BEN DALY

Web & Mobile
Team

SKILLS

Python, PHP, HTML/CSS, R, XML, SQL (Postgres, MySQL, Microsoft SQL Server), AWS, Unix Shell, Flask, Django, PostGIS, VSCode

INTERESTS

Data Visualisation, 3D Graphics, Virtual Simulation, Video Game Development, Gamification

Ben joined the team in September 2023. His background is in geospatial/GIS development, particularly in the environmental/conservation fields. He has previously developed Deep Learning Convolutional Neural Networks to identify native vegetation from multispectral images taken via drone.

Ben has worked in a wide range of technical roles in both the public and private sectors in the UK, US, NZ, Australia and Spain.

Research Software
Engineer

IMRE DRASKOVITS

Web & Mobile
Team

SKILLS

Swift, JavaScript, Adobe Photoshop, SwiftUI,
AWS, React Native

INTERESTS

iOS & Mac, App Publishing, Open Source,
Collaboration

Since joining in 2022, Imre has been working to move the RSE Web and Mobile Team towards an exciting new direction. Having a diverse background in mobile app development, he specialises in Apple mobile phone applications.

Imre is actively leading the development and maintenance of mobile phone applications for seven University research initiatives.

Having spent the past 5 years in software development, a key-factor in his career was working at a consulting firm; where he kick-started his career in mobile app development for an industry leading financial firm.

Operations
Administrator

MICHELLE GILBRIDE

Leadership Team

Michelle is the team's Operations Administrator providing support across all the activities we undertake. Michelle joined the team in September 2022 having previously worked in a range of public and private sector organisations both in the UK and abroad.

Michelle supports the Head of Research Software Engineering with meeting management, logistical support and event planning. In addition, Michelle supports the team's training offering, organising teaching spaces, registration and catering.

Outside of work Michelle enjoys football, music and exploring new places.

Research Software
Engineer

DAVID HERBERT

Web & Mobile
Team

SKILLS

JavaScript (React, Vue, Alpine), HTML/CSS (Tailwind, Bulma), Python, Java, PHP, C/C++, Perl, Bash shell, Docker, PostgreSQL/PostGIS, Desktop GIS (QGIS, ArcGIS), Geospatial and Mapping Web Systems, OpenLayers, Geoserver

INTERESTS

Full-stack Web Development, UI/UX, Web Design, AWS, DevOps, Docker

David graduated with a MA in Natural Sciences (Physics) from Cambridge University in 1986, before following a long career in the software industry. This included 10 years working as a freelance Web Developer. Before joining the Newcastle RSE team, David worked for 12 years for the British Antarctic Survey, completing large Full-Stack geospatial web development projects in Antarctica and Tasmania.

Since joining the RSE team in April 2019, he has designed and implemented principally mapping/geospatial web applications for a number of research projects and supported students on the Geospatial CDT programme.

Senior Research
Software Engineer

DAVE HORSFALL

Haniffa Lab

SKILLS

Python, PHP, JavaScript, HTML/CSS, JSON/XML, CI/CD, Laravel, Flask, Docker, MySQL, VSCode, GCP/AWS/Azure, Terraform, GitHub Workflows

INTERESTS

Web Development, Cloud Infrastructure

Dave joined the team in March 2020, and works as a full stack web developer. He graduated with a masters in Theoretical Physics from the University of Durham and has worked in both the open source community and the private sector. He works mainly with Python and Laravel, with a focus on a user-centered design process.

During his time in the team, he has trained as a Software Carpentries instructor and supervised Masters level dissertation students. He has also been awarded a Software Sustainability Institute fellowship to research mental health in the wider research software community.

Research Software
Engineer

RICHARD HOWEY

Middleware & Data
Science Team

SKILLS

C++, R, Python, Java, JavaScript, HTML/CSS, PHP,
Shell, SQL, LaTeX, GIMP, Davinci Resolve

INTERESTS

Mathematics, Mathematical Modelling, Statistics,
Genetics, Epidemiology

Richard has an extensive background working in different areas of Mathematics, Statistics and Computer Science. He completed his PhD in Pure Mathematics working in the field of functional analysis and after briefly working in the software industry, he worked in the field of Artificial Intelligence Planning at Durham and Strathclyde Universities.

Prior to joining the RSE group he has worked for over 10 years within the School of Medicine at Newcastle University in the field of Statistical Genetics developing methods and software to analyse genetic and biological data. During this time, he has also completed an MSc in Statistics (part-time at Sheffield University).

Research Software
Engineer

**BOWEN
LI**

**Middleware & Data
Science Team**

SKILLS

C/C++, Java, Python, Docker, Unix Shell, Latex,
Sphinx, Git/Github

INTERESTS

Computational Biology, Mathematical Modelling,
Numerical Simulation, Formal Verification,
Machine learning

Bowen Li joined the team in October 2022. His background centres on computational modelling, including both theory and application. He has many years experience in research software development. Li received his PhD in 2017 working on the formal modelling and verification of complex evolving system (CES). Since then, he has been involved in several computational biology projects as Research Associate.

During his RA career, Li was the main developer of open-source scientific software NUFEB (Massively parallel simulator for agent-based modelling of microbial systems); SONCraft (GUI-based platform for CES modelling and analysis); and mcSTACK (Probabilistic model checker for DNA nano-device model).

Research Software
Engineer

SI LINSLEY

Web & Mobile
Team

SKILLS

C#, JavaScript, Visual Studio, MSSQL, Azure,
.NET, ASP

INTERESTS

Full Stack Web Development

Si joined the Research Software Engineering team in September 2023. He's an enthusiastic developer who enjoys solving problems and leveraging the cloud.

His tech career started in IT Support in the travel industry before moving into Test Engineering in fintech and then onto Software Engineering in fintech for the last 4 years, working on a variety of web projects using the Microsoft ecosystem.

Outside of software development he's a keen traveller, having just spent 6 months exploring from New Zealand to Japan. He also loves to climb, read and explore spooky places.

Research Software
Engineer

ROBIN NANDI

Middleware & Data
Science Team

SKILLS

Python, R, C++
SQL, Strapi
GitHub, Docker
AWS, GCP, Oracle

INTERESTS

Application Build, DevOps, Cloud Infrastructure,
Machine Learning

Robin Nandi graduated with a MSc in Physics from Imperial College in 2008 followed by a PhD from the same university in 2012. He has worked in Software, Consultancy and Data Science roles in Financial Services including for PwC and Atom Bank.

He started in the Research Software Engineering team at Newcastle University in April 2022, contributing to a number of different data science and machine learning projects. He is also an elected trustee of the UK RSE Society.

Research Software
Engineer

BECKY OSSELTON

Head of Web
& Mobile Team

SKILLS

JavaScript, HTML/CSS, Python, PHP, Perl
Software: Vue.js, Laravel, CakePhp, WordPress,
ElasticSearch, Postgres, MySQL, SqlServer,
Docker, Tailwind, Bulma, Bootstrap

INTERESTS

Healthcare Applications, Educational Technology

Becky is a full stack web developer with many years of experience working in both the public and private sector. She graduated with an MSc in Computing Science in 1999 from Newcastle University. She joined the RSE team in 2019 and manages the Web and Mobile team.

Becky was previously employed with the NHS developing a healthcare application to modernise clinical practice for the Newcastle upon Tyne Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust. Becky continues with work closely with NHS Trusts on various projects. She is interested in inspiring young people and women to engage and seek careers in the technology sector.

Research Software
Engineer

JOHN SCHONEBOOM

Web & Mobile
Team

SKILLS

JavaScript, HTML/CSS, SQL, PHP, MySQL,
CakePHP, JQuery, Leaflet, Angular

INTERESTS

UI/UX, Web Design, Data Design

John comes to the RSE Team from his previous gig at Newcastle University as a research software engineer for ECPPEC (Eighteenth Century Political Participation and Electoral Culture), where he developed the database that drives that project's website.

He also works as a consultant for the New York State Department of Health, updating data on a monthly basis for their Health Profiles site, which allows end users to explore and compare quality data for hospitals, nursing homes, and other health care facilities.

Research Software
Engineer

GABRIELLE SCHROEDER

Middleware & Data
Science Team

SKILLS

Python, R, MATLAB, HTML/CSS, Git/GitHub,
LaTeX, Adobe Creative Cloud, Quarto

INTERESTS

Data Analysis, Data Visualisation, Signal
Processing, Network Analysis, Unsupervised
Learning, Statistics, Computational Modelling

Gabrielle Schroeder joined the team as a data scientist in September 2023. After undergraduate training in molecular biology and genetics, she transitioned to computational research in 2014 by pursuing an MSc in Neuroinformatics at Newcastle University, where she developed models of spreading dynamics on brain networks.

She continued her research in computational neuroscience at the university as a PhD student and postdoctoral researcher. Her work focused on developing pipelines and applying a variety of techniques, such as time series analysis and unsupervised learning, to analyse brain activity and clinical data. In addition to data analysis, her interests include data visualisation and software design.

Research Software
Engineer

MIKE SIMPSON

Middleware & Data
Science Team

SKILLS

Python, C++, Java, PHP, HTML & CSS,
JavaScript, Blender, PowerBI, WordPress,
Photoshop, OpenGL, PhysX, Unity

INTERESTS

Data Visualisation, 3D Graphics, Virtual
Simulation, Video Game Development,
Gamification

Dr Mike Simpson has a BSc in Computing and an MSc in Computer Games Engineering. He worked as a Game Programmer for several years before returning to the university to start his PhD in 2011. His thesis involved using software and development practices from the games industry to develop and evaluate real-time engineering simulations.

Since joining the RSE Team in 2018, he has worked on a number of projects, including with the NHS and the Alan Turing Institute. He has presented his work at several international events, including the Blender Conference, the UK RSE Conference and the IEEE e-Science Conference. He has also been involved in the wider RSE community, including being on the organising committee for the 2022 & 2023 RSE Conferences and is now a trustee of the UK RSE Society.

Research Software
Engineer

TIAGO SOUSA GARCIA

Web & Mobile Team

SKILLS

HTML/CSS, JavaScript, XML, XSLT, TEI, C,
Python, R, Flask, Svelte, Tailwind, React, Docker,
GitHub Workflows

INTERESTS

Web Development, Text Analysis, Digital
Humanities, AI, MLOps

Tiago is a frontend web developer and digital humanist. Before his graduate and post-graduate education in literature, he worked as a software developer and studied computer engineering in Portugal. Between 2017 and 2021, he was the Research Associate for the ATNU project, based at the School of English, where he also taught literary and digital humanities' focused modules.

In 2020-2021, he convened and ran the *Coding for Humanists* study group, and from 2022 he is one of the co-convenors of the Code Community at Newcastle University. Until 2022 he was a co-managing editor of the *Journal of the Text Encoding Initiative* and an editorial assistant for *The Programming Historian*.

Senior Research
Software Engineer

JANNETTA STEYN

Middleware & Data
Science Team

SKILLS

Java, JavaScript, Python, R, MatLab, HTML/CSS, PHP, C/C++, Tcl/Tk, Git, Unix Shell, Docker, OpenRefine, MongoDB, Postgres

INTERESTS

Carpentries Instructor Trainer, Computational Modelling, Bioinformatics, Data processing and analysis, High Performance Computing

After many years in industry as a software engineer Dr. Jannetta Steyn returned to university to study for a Masters in Bioinformatics followed by a PhD in computational neuroscience. She then joined the Bioinformatics Support Unit of Newcastle University for two and a half years after which she worked as a Senior Research Associate in the School of Computing.

In 2019 she joined the Research Software Engineering Team as a Senior Research Software Engineer. In 2020 she qualified as a Carpentries Instructor and has since taken the lead in organising and instructing Software Carpentries workshops at the University. In 2021 she also qualified as a Carpentries Instructor Trainer.

Research Software
Engineer

ALEX SURTEES

Web & Mobile
Team

SKILLS

JavaScript, HTML/CSS, R, SQL, React, Angular, d3, RShiny Dashboards

INTERESTS

Health Economic Models, UX Design

Alex is a full-stack web developer with experience developing health economic dashboards for communicating the cost-effectiveness of health interventions. He has also built statistical models to analyse the impact of diseases on patients and the effectiveness of health interventions, using techniques such as network meta-analyses and regression.

Alex is interested in learning new technologies and disciplines and applying his skills to a diverse range of meaningful projects.

Research Software
Engineer

FRANCES TURNER

Middleware & Data
Science Team

SKILLS

Matlab, Python, R, bash, NEURON, C, Unity, FSL,
Docker, Blender, Inkscape, LaTeX, Adobe
Creative Cloud, GitHub Workflows, Virtual Box

INTERESTS

Data Analysis, Mathematical Modelling, Network
Analysis, Dynamical Systems, Machine Learning,
Spiking Neural Networks, Neuroimaging, UI, HPC

Dr. Frances Turner (née Hutchings) has worked as a Research Software Engineer for the Digital Institute since June 2019. She first joined Newcastle University in 2013 to study for a Masters in Neuroinformatics, which led to a PhD and then RA positions based in the School of Computing with a focus on applying computational solutions to neuroscience questions.

During her tenure as a Research Software Engineer Frances has qualified as a Software Carpentries Instructor and has been able to develop computational solutions to a wide variety of projects from across all three faculties, picking up skills in machine learning, data science and user interface design.

Head of Research
Software Engineering

MARK TURNER

Leadership Team

SKILLS

JavaScript, TypeScript, HTML/CSS, Python, Java, PHP, C#.NET, Angular, VueJS, React, React Native, WordPress, MongoDB, Elasticsearch, Postgres, Terraform, Adobe Creative Cloud, GitHub Workflows

INTERESTS

UI/UX, Web Design, Azure, AWS, DevOps, Containers, Docker, Kubernetes, Serverless

Mark has led the Research Software Engineering team since its creation in 2018, growing it organically from a team of two to now twenty-five. During that time he has delivered multiple software projects across a wide range of disciplines, and now exclusively works on team management, policy & strategy, and research engagement.

He graduated with a BSc in Computing from Northumbria University in 2008 followed by an MSc from Newcastle University in 2012. In 2016 he was elected as a trustee for the UK Research Software Engineering Association, contributing to the transformation of the association into a registered charity in 2018. In 2022 he was the programme chair for the UK RSE Conference.

Research Software
Engineer

REECE WALSH

Web & Mobile
Team

SKILLS

React, JavaScript, TypeScript, Java, Kotlin, React Native, JUnit, Jest, Cypress, Node.js, .NET, Express, MongoDB, Springboot, MySQL, Figma

INTERESTS

Web Development, Native App Development, UX Design, Pathfinding Algorithms

Reece joined the Research Software Engineering team in March 2023 while completing his masters in Computer Science at Newcastle University. His dissertation project was to develop a pathfinding algorithm visualiser that allowed users to interact and experiment with different pathfinding algorithms in the hope of furthering their understanding when paired with traditional academic methods.

Since joining the team Reece has worked on a full-stack web application, a native mobile application and has begun to re-design and implement an existing full-stack system for an ongoing NHS Foundation Trust project.

Research Software
Engineer

ROBIN WARDLE

Middleware & Data
Science Team

SKILLS

C / C++, Java, Javascript, FORTRAN, HTML / CSS,
Unix shells, Python, Modelica, Matlab, Docker,
MongoDB, OpenModelica / Dymola, Terraform,
LaTeX, Blender, GitHub Workflows, Gimp

INTERESTS

System modelling and simulation, Numerical
methods, Data processing and analysis,
Visualisation. Cloud Computing.

Robin joined the Research Software Engineering team in May 2021, on completing a PhD in Energy at Newcastle University. He graduated with a Masters in Electro-mechanical Engineering from Manchester University and has additionally worked as an RA in Newcastle University's School of Engineering on energy systems demonstrator and modelling projects. He has also worked extensively in industry, principally in scientific and simulation software environments, and has significant project management experience in both industrial and university contexts.

As well as developing data and software solutions for research, Robin is a qualified Software Carpentries Instructor and also teaches Degree Apprenticeship modules in collaboration with the School of Computing.

THE PROJECTS

ACHILLES

PRINCIPLE INVESTIGATOR
ROSS STIRLING

RICHARD HOWEY

The ACHILLES programme comprises a unique consortium of established and future-leading academics in the fields of civil and geotechnic engineering. Their expertise span embankments and cuttings, soil mechanics, and the impact of climate and climate change. There were two main objectives of RSE involvement in this project, firstly the collection of environmental sensor data from an embankment at Nafferton Farm. The aim was to automate the retrieval of this data by implementing resilient, low-powered infrastructure suitable for field deployment. Secondly, an RSE was needed to help set up a thermal camera and accompanying night-time camera to take images of a lysimeter (big pot of earth) at regular intervals throughout the year standing outside the USB university building. The camera needed a program (in C++ using the camera company's SDK) to be written to take temperature data so that an image with a temperature scale can be plotted and saved.

FUNDER

EPSRC

PROJECT AWARD

£ 4.8M

AI-PSORT

PRINCIPLE INVESTIGATOR

NICK REYNOLDS

BOWEN LI

Psoriasis is a common, chronic, potentially disfiguring disease that affects more than 1 million people in the UK. It can cause considerable psychological and social disability. In the past 10 years there has been a dramatic improvement in clinical outcomes for patients with severe psoriasis due to the introduction of a new class of injectable drugs called biologics. However, these drugs are very expensive and not all patients respond. The project aims at closing this gap by using Artificial Intelligence approaches to develop personalised biologic therapies and computational models that can reliably predict the outcome of biologic therapies.

The RSE role aims develop an agent-based model and software for simulating epidermal cell dynamics and their responds to the treatments. The simulation would allow us to gain insights into how immune cytokine stimuli induce hyperproliferation in psoriasis to better understand disease formation, structural changes, and the recovery from biologic treatment.

FUNDER

ROSETREES TRUST

PROJECT AWARD

£ 250K

BEE-ING HUMAN

PRINCIPLE INVESTIGATOR
JENNIFER RICHARDS

TIAGO SOUSA GARCIA

Bee-ing Human is an interdisciplinary research project gathering researchers and practitioners from literary studies, musicology, digital humanities and biology (animal behaviour). It centres on a seventeenth-century apiculture book, Charles Butler's *The Feminine Monarchy of Bees*, using it both as an object of study and as a departure point to contrast the early modern knowledge and culture around bees and beekeeping with the latest research in animal behaviour and emotion. Literary scholars will study and edit Butler's original text, musicologists will study the compositions included in Butler's writing, as well as respond with new compositions and reinterpretations of the sound of bees and research results; biologists, inspired by Butler's work, will work on the emotional states of bees.

The RSE is responsible for creating the final output (the digital hub that will become the new bee book) that will gather all the material and research produced during the project, digital experiments to communicate the research methods employed by the different disciplines, as well as coordinate and oversee the digital editing component of the project.

FUNDER

LEVERHULME TRUST

PROJECT AWARD

£ 442K

BEYOND THE MARGINS

PRINCIPLE INVESTIGATOR
IAN JOHNSON

JOHN SCHONEBOOM

Explorer, writer, archaeologist, and colonial diplomat Gertrude Bell (1868-1926) witnessed and recorded events of significant geopolitical importance throughout her life, particularly in the Middle East. This project builds on the Gertrude Bell Archive collection of some twelve thousand digitised images of Bell's photographs, letters, and diary entries. Each document belongs to a certain location and time and is linked, along with transcriptions and other contextual information, through an interactive map with date-range controls. The site also dedicates feature space to a series of mapped-out Gertrude Bell stories based on documents selected from the archive enhanced by customized narrative text.

FUNDER

PRIVATE ENDOWMENT

PROJECT AWARD

£ 112K

...eth bound to a piller, his head downward
...nd Roasted.

BRITISH PRINTED IMAGES

PRINCIPLE INVESTIGATOR
ADAM MORTON

BECKY OSSELTON

British Printed Images to 1700 is a digital library of prints and book illustrations from early modern Britain. The legacy website no longer functions correctly and is being rebuilt with a modern technology stack by the RSE team. It features a searchable database of digitised images taken from the Department of Prints and Drawings at the British Museum, and the Department of Word and Image at the Victoria and Albert Museum.

Prints can be searched for by producer, by name of person depicted, or by subject. It is possible to combine various search criteria and apply a date filter to bring back the desired result set. The archive management has been transferred from King's College London to Newcastle University and Adam Morton in the School of Arts and Cultures.

FUNDER

AHRC

PROJECT AWARD

£ 29K

CATTLE SMART

PRINCIPLE INVESTIGATOR
MATT LEACH

BOWEN LI

The aim of this project was to develop an automated weight prediction tool that employed Machine Learning algorithms to evaluate the weight of cattle through image analysis. Traditionally, determining the weight of livestock has been a manual and labour-intensive task. The project sought to revolutionise the process by introducing a more automated and efficient solution.

The specific role of the RSE team involved utilising object detection to pre-processing cattle video data and implementing image regression for weight prediction. Both methods fell under the domain of computer vision tasks, with object detection dedicated to identifying and locating the object of interest (in our case, cattle) within images or videos. On the other hand, image regression learns to predict a continuous set of numbers (specifically weights) derived from input cattle images. Our model demonstrated a strong performance with an average prediction error of 12.72%. The outcome highlighted the potential to extend the applicability of this technology to other livestock animals, enabling real-time weight assessments through various devices and expanding its use in diverse applications.

FUNDER

NORTHERN ACCELERATOR

PROJECT AWARD

£ 50K

CLIMATE CHAMP

PRINCIPLE INVESTIGATOR
VIKTORIA SPAISER

IMRE DRASKOVITS

REECE WALSH

ROBIN WARDLE

According to the UK Government Climate Change Committee at least 59% of the measures to meet UK's Net Zero goal require behavioural and societal change. The project created a mobile app that allowed users to track their carbon footprint throughout their day for an 8 week trial period, while receiving prompts to make small behavioural changes.

The experiment measured two groups of participants. Every day, the experimental group received reminders about environmental concerns and recorded their daily activities, while the remaining control group received no prompts from the reminders and solely logged their activities.

The user were able to view their weekly carbon footprint through simple graphs. Feedback from the app users was very positive with the vast majority stating that using the app had made them think more about green issues during their daily lives.

FUNDER

UKRI

PROJECT AWARD

£ 38K

COLOURING CITIES

PRINCIPLE INVESTIGATOR
POLLY HUDSON

MIKE SIMPSON

The building stock is a city's most significant socio-cultural and economic resource and its largest capital asset. Buildings are also where we spend most of our lives and most of our money, and where enormous potential for energy and waste reduction lies. To improve the quality, sustainability and resilience of building stocks, and to help reduce emissions from them, comprehensive information on their composition, operation and dynamic behaviour are now required. However, in many countries relevant data are extremely difficult to obtain, often highly fragmented, restricted, missing or only available in aggregated form.

Colouring Cities sets out to address this issue. The initiative develops open code designed to facilitate the construction and management of low cost, open data platforms, providing twelve types of data on buildings, at building level. These are needed to answer questions such as: How many buildings do we have? Which building types, uses, construction systems, ages, styles and sizes are located where? How repairable, adaptable and extendable are they? How long could they last if properly maintained? How energy efficient are they?

FUNDER
UKRI

PROJECT AWARD
£ 120K

CONBOTS

PRINCIPLE INVESTIGATOR
DOMENICO FORMICA

MIKE SIMPSON

CONBOTS is an international research project aiming to develop robots to promote physical communication during handwriting and music learning. As part of CONBOTS, a group of researchers in the Newcastle School of Engineering have developed an experiment involving a game where the user must use a robot arm to move a green marker to a red marker on a vertical monitor screen.

The RSE team was tasked with converting the game into a 3D holographic application to run on a Microsoft HoloLens device. The intention is to allow the user to move the coloured dot markers in an Augmented Reality (AR) horizontal space.

FUNDER
ERC

PROJECT AWARD
£ 4.1M

CYBER SECURITY GAMES

PRINCIPLE INVESTIGATOR
STEVE MCGOUGH

RICHARD HOWEY

ROBIN NANDI

Attacks and defence of a network of computers can be seen as an adversarial competition (or a game) between two sets of agents: attackers and defenders. We propose separating the concepts of the cause (the method used to achieve the attack) from the symptoms (what the attack achieves on the system).

We will use Reinforcement Learning (RL), a form of Machine Learning in which an agent is provided with a view of the state of the system and learns the correct (sequence of) action to perform to achieve their goal. The Red agent seeks to compromise the system, while the Blue agent seeks to protect the system. By training in a confrontational game, both agents will become better at achieving their goal.

FUNDER

EPSRC

PROJECT AWARD

£ 95K

DEEP LEARNING FOR REAL-TIME SPECTROSCOPIC ANALYSIS

PRINCIPLE INVESTIGATOR
THOMAS PENFOLD

BOWEN LI

ALEX SURTEES

X-ray Spectroscopy is a technique that allows a deep understanding of the geometric, electronic, and spin structure of various materials. The main goal of this project is to develop an easy-to-use and efficient tool that leverages state-of-the-art machine learning techniques for the fast and automated analysis and prediction of x-ray spectroscopy data.

The AI modelling team (BL, KG, and NA) aims to develop a Spectrum-Structure Prediction DNN (Deep Neural Networks) tool enabling generalisability across spectrum and structure - predicting either the structure of a material based on the given spectrum, or conversely, predicting the spectrum based on the known structure. Additionally, the tool should provide information about the uncertainty of the model's predictions, enabling users to assess the reliability and confidence of the results.

The UI development team (AS) aims to develop graphical user interface (GUI) allowing end-users to upload structures of their molecules or materials, element and absorption edge and technique of interest, and make predictions.

FUNDER
EPSRC

PROJECT AWARD
£ 1.3M

DEGREE APPRENTICESHIP

PRINCIPLE INVESTIGATOR
STEVE RIDDLE

BECKY OSSELTON

ROBIN WARDLE

The Institute of Coding (IoC) is a government funded initiative to help close the digital skills gap in businesses. The IoC at Newcastle University has three postgraduate qualifications to improve digital skills in the North East and beyond. These apprenticeships in computing aid experienced professionals or recent graduates to further develop their skills and knowledge in either data analytics or cyber security. A software engineering option is a conversion route allowing non-IT specialists to develop broad digital skills to work in IT.

The RSE team has been able to support the School of Computing by providing teaching resource for the Degree Apprenticeship programme. The team re-developed content for two modules: CSC8425 Business Applications and CSC8235 Web Client Applications. These modules were delivered in a blended mode of online sessions and in-person seminars.

FUNDER

NEWCASTLE UNIVERSITY

PROJECT AWARD

£ 11.8K

DOLFIN

PRINCIPLE INVESTIGATOR
JEREMY PARR

KATE COURT

IMRE DRASKOVITS

MIKE SIMPSON

DOLFIN was a collaboration between Newcastle University School of Pharmacy and the National Perinatal Epidemiology Unit at Oxford University. The project involved conducting a clinical trial to evaluate the effect of a nutritional supplement on babies who are born prematurely or who suffer poor blood supply or lack of oxygen to the brain before or around birth.

The RSE Team developed a cross-platform mobile app to aid the clinical trial via data collection from parents. Participants are expected to report their babies' supplement intake daily in the first 28 days of the trial. Following the first month, they report back on a weekly basis to the medical team for a year. The research runs on an annual basis with various participants.

Data submitted by the parents is later surveyed by a medical expert team. They deduct long term feed supplementation effects in neonates, hoping to improve shape the babies' cognitive development towards a rewarding bright direction.

FUNDER

NIHR

PROJECT AWARD

£193K

EPRASE

PRINCIPLE INVESTIGATOR
STEPHANIE KLEIN

BECKY OSSELTON

ePRaSE is a 3-year project to take forward a previous software pilot to allow NHS Trusts in England to evaluate the mitigation of risk in their e-Prescribing systems. The RSE team has been commissioned to develop the pilot tool further, with an eventual aim for it to become a standardised assessment exercise undertaken annually by Trusts.

The RSE team has been working closely with the Newcastle Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust to develop test patients for the system and suitable clinical scenarios. Currently focused on adult patients, there are plans to expand the tool to include mental health and paediatric scenarios.

FUNDER

NHS ENGLAND

PROJECT AWARD

£ 290K

FEEDS

PRINCIPLE INVESTIGATOR

JEREMY PARR

IMRE DRASKOVITS

DAVID HERBERT

The FEEDS Toolkit is an evidence-based toolkit resource that explains the background to the eating and drinking of children with a neurodisability, and the interventions that can be used to improve safe feeding. The Toolkit has been written by multidisciplinary professionals with expertise in identifying eating, drinking, and swallowing difficulties (EDSD), and making recommendations about how best to ensure young people receive fluid and food safely and efficiently. It is designed to be used by parents of children and young people with EDSD and by NHS multidisciplinary health professionals (HPs) to identify and prioritise interventions relevant to an individual child; it does not replace professional support.

The FEEDS Toolkit is a clinical and evidence-based resource was created following clinical research led by multidisciplinary colleagues at Newcastle University and Newcastle upon Tyne Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust. RSE involvement is the creation of a secure informational website for use by parents, allowing trialling of different interventions under clinical guidance, communication enabled via an embedded chat application.

FUNDER

NIHR

PROJECT AWARD

£ 308K

FIRM2

PRINCIPLE INVESTIGATOR
RICHARD DAWSON

JANNETTA STEYN

ROBIN WARDLE

Actions taken before, during and after the shock of flood infrastructure failure can lead to radically different outcomes. Poor warnings, slow evacuation, or failure to erect temporary flood defence infrastructure all reduce resilience, increase damages and threaten lives. The Flood Infrastructure Resilience Model (FIRM) is a coupled agent-based and hydrodynamic flood model built on a geospatial data architecture that is used to explore the impact of the flood infrastructure failure on flood resilience, and to test strategies to mitigate the impact of these shocks. FIRM integrates remotely sensed information on topography, buildings and road networks with empirical survey data to fit characteristics of specific communities. Simulation of individuals has been coupled with a hydrodynamic model to assess their resilience in the event of flooding.

The aim of this project is to re-code FIRM into Python for greater interoperability, integrate FIRM onto DAFNI to make it more accessible to the community, to enhance FIRM by adding new functionality to test a wider set of flood resilience actions, and to provide virtual and in-person training to support the wider uptake of the model and DAFNI.

FUNDER

DAFNI

PROJECT AWARD

£ 54K

GEOSPATIAL SYSTEMS CDT

PRINCIPLE INVESTIGATOR
JON MILLS

DAVID HERBERT

The CDT is an integrated collaboration between Newcastle University and the University of Nottingham, two world leading centres of Geospatial Systems research. Drawing on experts from across Newcastle University, the CDT is a unique opportunity for academia to work with the geospatial industry to address major global societal issues, such as climate change impacts, urban sustainability, spatially resourcing public health, and removing spatial barriers to social inclusion and healthy ageing. The RSE team support this effort through a dedicated resource for software development advice and guidance to students, ensuring code produced from the CDT is of a high standard for reuse in the geospatial community.

FUNDER

EPSRC

PROJECT AWARD

£ 6.7M

HANIFFA LAB

PRINCIPLE INVESTIGATOR
MUZLIFAH HANIFFA

DANIELA BASURTO LOZADA

DAVE HORSFALL

The Haniffa lab is a leader in the international Human Cell Atlas initiative to systematically map all cells in the body and across the lifespan. The lab applies disruptive omics technologies to study human cells at single-cell resolution using of state-of-the-art single cell technologies to understand how the immune system develops and maintains health, the consequences of infection, inflammation and disease. It provides a multifaceted computing infrastructure including a powerful LSF cluster, GPU access, an OpenStack cloud architecture, and easy access to interactive notebooks for convenient day-to-day data analysis.

The Haniffa Lab has an embedded team of RSEs that sit between the lab and the centralised RSE team at Newcastle University. The embedded team benefits from exposure to the skills and resources provided through the centralised facility but is fully integrated within the lab and committed to their research aims. The team works closely with bioinformaticians and computational biologists to deliver the key objectives across several research areas.

FUNDER

WELLCOME TRUST

PROJECT AWARD

£ 112K

HDBR

PRINCIPLE INVESTIGATOR
STEVEN LISGO

SI LINSLEY

ALEX SURTEES

HDBR stands for Human Developmental Biology Resource. The HDBR is a tissue bank that stores human embryonic and fetal tissues and has been collecting these since 1999. During this time, tissue provided by the HDBR has helped support numerous important research projects in many different countries. The website developed for HDBR is a UI for accessing information in the database for researchers and admins to view project information, manage tissue requests and updated related information such as researchers on the project, publications and storage information.

RSEs have been optimising the legacy database to streamline the development of the front-end system.

FUNDER
MRC

PROJECT AWARD
£ 115K

INVASIVE WATER HYACINTH

PRINCIPLE INVESTIGATOR
DEEPAYAN BHOWMIK

BEN DALY

The project aimed to map the extent of invasive Water Hyacinth growth across selected regions of India using downloaded satellite imagery in combination with a recognition algorithm to identify Hyacinth density along riparian water channels. Currently, invaded areas are spotted using arial drones and the plants are removed manually.

The team has produced a tool where satellite imagery is downloaded for a select region defined as a polygon, preprocessed for colour balance, fed into the recognition algorithm, and outputted as a series of layers onto a front-end mapping web interface. Each layer is delineated by Hyacinth density and has the option to toggle on/off via a user selectable button.

FUNDER

ROYAL ACADEMY OF ENGINEERING

PROJECT AWARD

£ 15K

MOUSE MAPP

PRINCIPLE INVESTIGATOR
MATT LEACH

MARK TURNER

Millions of mice are used worldwide in research each year (EU statistical report 2019). Ensuring any pain or suffering is kept to a minimum requires careful monitoring of the animals so that appropriate action can be taken, and humane endpoints implemented. Welfare is monitored using a panel of indicators such as the assessment of pain, body and coat condition, and the weight of the animal.

Traditional methods of assessment based on monitoring changes in behaviour or clinical signs (e.g. weight loss) are time consuming and can have other limitations as they may not be specific to pain or a sensitive indicator of health under certain conditions. A number of scoring systems (e.g. the mouse grimace scale and body condition scoring) have been developed that provide simple, reliable and non-invasive measures for assessing welfare at the cage side (Langford et al., 2010; Leach et al., 2012; Ullman-Cullere and Foltz 1999), but there has not been widespread adoption.

FUNDER

NC3RS

PROJECT AWARD

£ 99K

NORMATIVE MODELLING OF NEUROIMAGING DATA

PRINCIPLE INVESTIGATOR
YUJIANG WANG

ALEX SURTEES

The project is developing a statistical model to analyse neuroimaging data using the normative modelling framework. The model allows researchers to assess the abnormality of brain morphology metrics across a wide range of brain regions in patients with neurological disorders, furthering our understanding of the patterns of clinical and biological markers in patients with complex, heterogeneous disorders. The Research Software Engineering team is ensuring the robustness of the model codebase and developing a web application to allow a wide range of researchers to run the powerful model being developed.

FUNDER
EPSRC

PROJECT AWARD
£ 750K

OPENCLIM

PRINCIPLE INVESTIGATOR
RICHARD DAWSON

FATIH CIGIRCI

A "search-and-view" type of tool in the form of a user-friendly web application that facilitated the exploration of OpenCLIM's project datasets. The datasets were systematically stored in JSON files, and subsequently transformed into multi-polygon structures that were presented on a LeafletJS map.

This tool aimed to enrich the user's exploration journey by integrating already existing advanced (geospatial) data structures with data presentation techniques.

The combination of systematic data organization, transformation into visual structures and presentation on an interactive map collectively contributed to a comprehensive and engaging user experience within the OpenCLIM ecosystem.

FUNDER
NERC

PROJECT AWARD
£ 1.9M

OPENSCAN2

PRINCIPLE INVESTIGATOR
TERESA FORTUNE

DAVID HERBERT

GABRIELLE SCHROEDER

ROBIN WARDLE

The OpenScan project collects, stores, and analyses international clinical trial and medical device data for horizon scanning research at the NIHR Innovation Observatory. Additionally, OpenScan is the basis for external resources such as ScanMedicine, "a novel searching system providing health care professionals, patients, carers, the public, decision- and policy-makers, and researchers with open access to the development pipeline underpinning health technology innovations" (Sadek et al., 2023). This complex project has become challenging to maintain and expand.

The role of the RSE team is to assess the back-end software and cloud computing infrastructure; design and implement new frameworks to improve collaboration, sustainability, and cost; and provide training for the Innovation Observatory developers for maintaining and expanding the project. Additionally, the frameworks provided by the RSE team will be used to develop infrastructures and pipelines for related work, allowing the Innovation Observatory to rapidly and robustly implement new projects.

FUNDER

NIHR

PROJECT AWARD

£ 130K

OPTIMISING THE TRAINING AND INFERENCE OF DEEP REINFORCEMENT LEARNING

PRINCIPLE INVESTIGATOR
**JACEK CALA &
STEPHEN MCGOUGH**

CARMELO CALAFIORE

RICHARD HOWEY

The goal of the project is to architecture, train and deploy models that optimally control a team of fighter jets and execute their military mission. We optimise the models for the task by reinforcement learning. We were given a simulation of an environment with aircrafts which can be fighter jets (the agents) and their missiles. The task is to fly the fighter jets over an objective, kill some enemy fighter jets with missiles, avoid getting killed by the enemy missiles, go back to the base and land on the base. The models were recurrent neural networks (RNNs) with multiple non-linear layers carry a memory of the previous observations for more stable predictions. The model input is an array of coordinates of the objective, base, and the detected aircrafts. The models are trained to predict the cumulative rewards for all possible agent action give the current input.

FUNDER

LEONARDO

PROJECT AWARD

£ 61K

ORGAN QUALITY ASSESSMENT

PRINCIPLE INVESTIGATOR
COLIN WILSON

KATE COURT

IMRE DRASKOVITS

ROBIN NANDI

FRANCES TURNER

REECE WALSH

We have developed a digital medical device to objectively evaluate organ quality and streamline the process of assessment (Organ Quality Assessment, OrQA). One facet is a secure, surgeon accessible internet platform for storing and sharing images – this will help speed up effective decision making and ensure the organ goes to a centre that will transplant. The second is an aligned software system that analyses the picture and objectively scores the "quality" of the organ. We have developed and tested OrQA using a historic set of images so far. The next phase of development will take pictures specifically for the device and test the software on a larger bank of images to ensure that the system works in the real world. Alongside this we need to ensure that the device is acceptable to patients, professionals and the public.

FUNDER
NIHR

PROJECT AWARD
£ 1.5M

PATIENT REGISTRY

PRINCIPLE INVESTIGATOR
FAI NG

FATIH CIGIRCI

REECE WALSH

RICHARD HOWEY

This web application has been designed as a dynamic and secure platform for a wide range of patient research groups seeking an efficient patient registry solution.

This application not only stores patient information securely but also enables patients to periodically complete condition-related questionnaires throughout the year. Its adaptable framework allows staff to independently update questionnaire content, thus bypassing the need for external parties.

The application's design includes a comprehensive admin dashboard, offering extensive customization and control. Registries have the capability to craft email templates, extract and analyse data, manage staff, establish roles, control permissions, and generate detailed reports derived from questionnaire responses. Additionally, they have the tools to efficiently handle and export patient data, further enhancing the application's utility and effectiveness.

FUNDER
MRC

PROJECT AWARD
£ 12K

PYRAMID

PRINCIPLE INVESTIGATOR

LIZ LEWIS

ROBIN WARDLE

Changing climate and the consequential expected increased risk of flooding suggests a role for a “near real-time” flood simulation and prediction tool. The PYRAMID project produced a demonstrator platform for the simulation of flood events, extending existing hydrological simulation tools to incorporate critical factors such as floating debris and more complex ground structure. The PYRAMID demonstrator has been produced using the Data & Analytics Facility for National Infrastructure (DAFNI), taking advantage of its large data storage, workflow orchestration, and visualisation capabilities to produce a coherent system for multi-level flood simulation using multiple data sources. The project successfully implemented a functioning workflow connecting a number of simulators, data processing models and datasets to provide a working illustration of a complex near-real-time flood modelling environment.

FUNDER

EPSRC

PROJECT AWARD

£ 787K

RHEUMATOLOGY SERVICE DATABASE

PRINCIPLE INVESTIGATOR
ARTHUR PRATT

BECKY OSSELTON

ROBIN WARDLE

The work consisted of 2 main strands, the MSK-RADAR project and the EARTH database.

MSK-RADAR established a pipeline for data from the Newcastle Hospitals NHS Trust E-PROMS system into the Trust's main patient care record system. E-PROMS records patient rheumatic musculoskeletal disease symptoms from online questionnaires. This involved RSEs working closely with Trust technical staff and completing Project Management process documentation.

The EARTH database is used by clinicians in the Newcastle Hospitals NHS Trust and Newcastle University Rheumatology research staff. It is used to record patient clinical data and also receives data from internal NHS systems. As an Access database application, it had become unstable and difficult to support. The RSE team worked with the Trust to find a suitable in-house solution that would give the correct levels of access to both the Trust and University staff.

FUNDER
MRC

PROJECT AWARD
£ 44K

ROCK ART IN OMAN

PRINCIPLE INVESTIGATOR
STEPHANIE DROPPER

IMRE DRASKOVITS

Rock Art is part of Oman's rich cultural heritage. The app's development and publishing process helps preserve this diverse environment. This cross-platform Android and Apple iPhone application provides English as well as a localised Arabic version for users based in Oman. This is reflected in the designing process. The mobile app is feature-rich in functioning both left-to-right as well as right-to-left design and text alignment.

Tracking and protecting the landscape filled with these panels via the application enhances accessibility for researchers accessing and categorising these precious remains of human history.

FUNDER

THYSSEN FOUNDATION

PROJECT AWARD

£ 338K

STATISTICAL GENETICS

PRINCIPLE INVESTIGATOR
HEATHER CORDELL

RICHARD HOWEY

Genome-wide association studies investigate genetic variation (changes to the DNA sequence) across the entire genome, to see which changes correlate with disease or disease-related outcomes. This project aims to both detect such correlations and understand the biological mechanisms behind them. The research includes measuring potential intermediate processes like gene expression (where DNA is transcribed to RNA), DNA methylation (the presence or absence of a chemical modification to the DNA sequence) and measurements of proteins (based on the amino acids into which RNA is translated), in a set of diseased and non-diseased individuals.

These measurements can also be extrapolated to other diseased and non-diseased individuals with genetic data available. An important part of this work is to develop improved statistical methods and accompanying software implementations in order to carry out the required data analyses. The work carried out allows a better understanding of the biological processes leading to disease development, and thus to propose potential therapies and cures.

FUNDER

WELLCOME TRUST

PROJECT AWARD

£ 1.5M

TYNE THEATRE DATABASE

PRINCIPLE INVESTIGATOR
ANDREW SHAIL

KATE COURT

An online calendar of all performances at the Tyne Theatre & Opera House from the venue's opening in September 1867 to its closure in March 1919 (51 years and 6 months), accessed via the current Tyne Theatre & Opera House's own website. As part of its National Lottery Heritage 'Drury Lane of the North' project, the Tyne Theatre & Opera House engaged with a team of roughly 25 local volunteers to build a calendar of every performance at the venue during its Victorian/Edwardian heyday. The calendar took the form of 52 spreadsheets, 52 text files and thousands of images. Andrew Shail approached the RSE team to develop a page on the Tyne Theatre & Opera House's website, powered by a Google Sheet, that acted as the interface that makes this calendar publicly accessible in a user-friendly browsable and searchable format.

FUNDER

NEWCASTLE UNIVERSITY

PROJECT AWARD

£ 3K

VNS CLOSE NIT

PRINCIPLE INVESTIGATOR
TIAGO DA SILVA COSTA

JANNETTA STEYN

FRANCES TURNER

The RSE team has developed lab-based closed-loop taVNS techniques, to allow the automated delivery of non-invasive vagal nerve stimulation at specific target points of the respiratory cycle, while monitoring effects on HRV, blood pressure, EEG and reaction times.

RSEs developed software to record and visualise data recorded from a NiDAQ U6229. The NiDAQ was connected to a DS8R DigiStim stimulating device and an AD Instrument Powerlab 4/26 amplifier for recording breathing with a breathing belt and/or nasal cannula. An EEG was used for capturing brain activity and a blood pressure/haemodynamic device for continuous blood pressure monitoring.

For assisting with the software development, RSEs also programmed an ESP8266 with a basic breathing model that produced a simulated breathing signal.

FUNDER

EPSRC

PROJECT AWARD

£ 90K

THE

THE FEEDBACK

FEEDBACK

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Working with a member of the Research Software Engineering (RSE) team was a game-changer for our research project. Robin's expertise in backend software development was excellent, bringing a depth of knowledge and skills that significantly enhanced the technical aspects of our work allowing the rest of the team to focus on their own subject-specific areas of research. By working with the RSE team, not only did we have access to Robin's skills, but also the ability to tap into the collective wisdom of the entire RSE team, which proved invaluable; their collaborative approach allowed us to address complex challenges more efficiently and creatively. The contribution of the RSE team, and our dedicated member in particular, was instrumental in the success of PYRAMID. Their expertise, collaborative spirit, and professionalism not only elevated the quality of our software development but also made the entire process enjoyable and efficient. I wholeheartedly recommend the RSE team to any research project in need of top-notch software engineering support.

Liz Lewis

Faculty of Science, Agriculture & Engineering

”

I have been working with RSE on a project to relaunch an archive that was digitised in 2006. The experience has been a positive one. I have been supported at every stage, from the first drafts of the funding application to the running of the project. Rebecca Osselton and I hold weekly meetings about the project. These provide updates about the process of rebuilding the archive, and Rebecca takes great pains to explain to me what options are available and what challenges we might face in a terms that someone as non-computer literate as me can understand. I have been heartened by these meetings, and feel I understand the technical aspects of the archive much more clearly than I did since the project began 2 months ago. From my perspective as a PI, what matters most is that I know I have a point of contact with whom I can raise any queries. I feel supported, and we have established clear ways of working on the project together.

Adam Morton

Faculty of Humanities & Social Sciences

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The RSE team were exceptionally helpful from the moment I contacted them. This included writing up and preparing the technical aspects of the grant proposal, as well as the formal costing. I worked closely with Jannetta and Frances, who brought incredible expertise and hard work, as well as a fabulous can-do attitude. They reached out to other people in the University, arranged for us to get access to facilities we wouldn't otherwise, and made the project better in every way. On top of all of this, they are also kind and friendly people, a genuine pleasure to spend time with. The admin side of things was easy, with costings and billing being done effectively and timely. I'm having a great experience working with the RSE team and look forward to future projects with them.

Tiago da Silva Costa

Faculty of Medical Sciences

THE

THE STRATEGY

STRATEGY

STRATEGY

OUR VISION FOR THE NEXT FIVE YEARS

SHORT TERM

The next 12 months in focus, where we look to strengthen our core services and optimise our processes. The expansion of the team in number and technical experience puts us in good position for growth, while we can continue to build on our reputation as a successful facility.

MEDIUM TERM

The next 2 years may bring significant changes for the team, which will potentially lead to new challenges and opportunities.

LONG TERM

In the next five years, we would expect a greater consolidation of our services in the University and new partnerships to have emerged.

STRATEGY

SHORT TERM

In the past year, the RSE team has moved into a more settled period with steady growth and more established processes. With positive changes, some of the previous year's challenges have been overcome. The standardised use of GitHub and templates for project management has mostly overcome issues around a lack of documentation. The two RSE sub-teams of Web and Mobile and Middleware are well embedded and cross-functional team working across larger projects has become more common. This aids projects by increasing the knowledge base within the team and benefits staff by exposing individuals to new skill areas.

The increasing use of tools such as HubSpot and our bespoke project management tool have also allowed more focused tracking of projects and staff. This has also allowed more accurate forecasting of workloads and anticipation of staffing requirements.

Many of our projects are becoming larger in scope and have longer timescales, which has helped with security of tenure. Our involvement with

grant writing at an earlier project stage has also helped ensure that expectations around RSE assistance are correctly scoped into projects. We will continue to sharpen and improve processes, as financial tracking and balancing the long-term staffing of RSEs with the correct skills is an ongoing challenge.

Our reputation within the University has developed positively in the past year and we have many PIs with whom we have established relationships. This has given us a solid grounding for future project work in many disciplines. Our RSE speaking tour across University schools and faculties was also a successful venture that stimulated interest in the team and helped bring in new projects. Our ability to deliver mobile projects has been an important part of extending our offering to the wider University and we expect this, as well as HPC provision, to be an area of growth in the coming years.

STRATEGY

MEDIUM TERM

In the medium term, we need to focus on what training is best for the University research community. We have the option of continuing with Carpentries lessons, developing more bespoke training packages or a combination of both. We could choose to employ an RSE with a specific teaching element of their role, this could also provide a flexible resource for the School of Computing (e.g. on the Degree Apprenticeship Programme).

Integrating internships into the RSE team could potentially provide us with a pipeline of future developers. Recruiting more RSEs has the benefit of relieving the pressure on projects but brings increasing line management responsibility. Recent team expansion has led to larger numbers of direct reports for managers. A definite change for the next year or so is that we will incorporate an element of HPC support to the team. There is University funding for 2 standard RSEs and a senior RSE position.

We will continue working with PIs to deliver new projects, now also with an option for exascale computing. This will make Newcastle one of several

institutions investing in government supported initiatives to facilitate cutting-edge research that depends on ultra-fast computing resource. We will also continue with dissemination activities across the university potentially organising events and workshops. We may work more closely with senior university staff to expand our outreach to new areas of the business.

Staff reward and recognition will also become even more important if highly skilled RSEs are to be retained. We intend to work with People Services and other senior leads to produce a more diverse set of technical career pathways as an alternative to the traditional line manager role. It is also likely we will focus on more targeted training within the team to upskill in areas where existing skills are sparse.

Increasing numbers in the team may eventually require us to move to a new physical office location.

STRATEGY

LONG TERM

In the longer term, patterns and trends in projects and research support will have emerged that will help us develop and embed the team further into University research culture. The team may have settled in size and some level of staff turnover will be expected, but the overall impact on our ability to deliver projects will be minimal. The two sub-teams may have diversified into multiple sub-teams, as the team grows in numbers and technical capability. There may be an expansion in the type of support that we offer to research infrastructure and projects.

We will have more stable finances through larger projects and better systems for financial tracking of RSE project allocations. Project management

processes will be optimized and new roles and responsibilities in the team may have emerged. Training programmes will be well established. We will have a better view of the future of the facility, based on many years of previous activities and will also have a clear vision of the things we want to achieve.

We will have stronger links to other University departments, teams and research units. There may also be closer ties to external partners such as NHS England and other Universities. Our range of services will have expanded and we will be recognized as being a core contributor to academic research activity.

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